

TYPOLOGY OF ENGLISH DICTIONARIES

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Abstract: The main emphasis in the article is on the stages of the emergence of English lexicology, the types and forms of the first dictionary samples. In addition, the information on the audience of the dictionaries and the suggestions of lexicographers on the types of dictionaries was comparatively analyzed.

Key words: Lexicography, general and special dictionaries, etymology, synchronic.

It appears that lexicographic culture can also be done using the linguistic and cultural dictionary. Since concepts are the fundamental building blocks of linguoculture, the emergence of concept dictionaries is an indication that the field is maturing as a science—a sign that takes the shape of information being recorded in dictionaries, as noted fairly by Yu.N. Karaulov. The study of concepts in language and culture has advanced to the point where developing a conceptuary is now a legitimate job.

The following thesis presents a comprehensive historical survey of English lexicography, tracing the evolution of English dictionaries from their earliest forms to the sophisticated classification systems used today. Dictionaries serve as invaluable repositories of information regarding a language's pronunciation, grammar, history, etymology, and translations. Additionally, they play a pivotal role in facilitating intercultural communication. The roots of English lexicography can be traced back to medieval England, where early lexicographers produced the first comprehensive dictionaries. However, it was not until the 17th century that dictionaries began to resemble their modern counterparts. Robert Cawdrey's "A Table Alphabeticall" (1604) is widely considered to be the first English dictionary. While this is a significant milestone, it is important to acknowledge the contributions of earlier lexicographers such as Sir Thomas Elyot, who published the Latin-English "Bibliotheca Eliotae" in 1538. Early dictionaries were often thematically organized, covering topics such as celestial bodies, animals, plants, and natural phenomena. Over time, lexicographers drew upon these earlier works to create more comprehensive and systematic dictionaries. The 17th century marked a turning point in the development of English lexicography, with the emergence of more substantial and systematically organized dictionaries. Thomas Blount's "Glossographia" (1656) was one of the first attempts to classify dictionaries into general and specialized categories. Samuel Johnson's "A Dictionary of the English Language" (1755) made a significant contribution to the field, although his classification system was not as explicit. The 19th century witnessed further advancements in English lexicography, with lexicographers such as Noah Webster and James Murray making significant contributions. Webster's "An American Dictionary of the English Language" (1828) introduced a classification based on the dictionary's intended purpose, categorizing dictionaries into school, academic, and universal types. Murray's "The New English Dictionary on Historical Principles" (1884-1928) was a

monumental work that emphasized the historical development of words and divided dictionaries into synchronic and diachronic categories. In the 20th century, lexicographers such as Zgusta, Cruz, Hartmann, Landau, Sinclair, and Hanston refined and expanded upon existing classification systems, considering factors such as the dictionary's purpose, target audience, and scope. These scholars developed more sophisticated typologies based on criteria such as whether a dictionary is prescriptive or descriptive, general or specialized, and monolingual or multilingual.

"Dictionaries are valuable repositories of information about a language's pronunciation, grammar, history, etymology, and translations. They are also essential tools for effective intercultural communication. The development and popularization of English lexicography have a long history. We can find the earliest examples of comprehensive English dictionaries in the works of lexicographers from medieval England. From 1604 onwards, dictionaries began to take on the form we recognize today. Robert Cawdrey's "A Table Alphabeticall" is widely considered to be the first English dictionary, although earlier works by lexicographers such as Sir Thomas Elyot laid the groundwork. According to A.H. Murray, many dictionaries created between the 11th and 15th centuries were thematically organized, covering topics like celestial bodies, animals, plants, and natural phenomena. Subsequent dictionaries built upon these earlier works, becoming more comprehensive and accessible. The 17th century saw the emergence of full-fledged English dictionaries, leading to the development of classification systems. Thomas Blount's "Glossographia" was one of the earliest attempts to categorize dictionaries into general and specialized types. Samuel Johnson's "A Dictionary of the English Language" made significant contributions to the field, although his classification system was less explicit.

The 19th century brought about further advancements in English lexicography, with lexicographers like Noah Webster and James Murray making notable contributions. Webster's "An American Dictionary of the English Language" introduced a classification based on the dictionary's purpose, while Murray's "The New English Dictionary on Historical Principles" emphasized the historical development of words. In the 20th century, lexicographers such as Zgusta, Cruz, Hartmann, Landau, Sinclair, and Hanston refined and expanded upon existing classification systems, considering factors like the dictionary's purpose, target audience, and scope. They developed more sophisticated typologies based on whether a dictionary is prescriptive or descriptive, general or specialized, and monolingual or multilingual. While dictionaries primarily serve as repositories of words and their meanings, they also encompass a wide range of information.

The classification of dictionaries has evolved over time, allowing for more precise categorization based on various criteria such as purpose, scope, and target audience."

In conclusion, dictionaries have played a pivotal role in the development and understanding of languages, particularly English. From their early thematic organization to modern-day classification systems, dictionaries have evolved to become comprehensive repositories of information. They serve as essential tools for language learners, researchers, and anyone seeking to deepen their understanding of a language. Beyond their linguistic value, dictionaries also contribute to intercultural communication by providing a shared reference point for understanding and interpreting language. The ongoing development of lexicography ensures that dictionaries remain relevant and adaptable to the ever-changing landscape of

language and communication. As technology continues to advance, we can expect dictionaries to evolve further, incorporating new features and functionalities to meet the needs of diverse users.

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